

Video conferencing software platforms: Perception, use and experiences among Indian students for learning amid COVID-19 pandemic times

Vysakh. C

Research Scholar

DOSR in Library & Information Science
Tumkur University, Karnataka, 572103.

Dr Rajendra Babu. H*

Assistant Professor

DOSR in Library & Information Science
Tumkur University, Karnataka-572103

Manu. BK

4th Semester MLISc Student

DOSR in Library & Information Science
Tumkur University, Karnataka, India-572103

Abstract

The pandemic has led to the closure of educational institutions in the country and entered into the process of distance education through web learning. The present study reports the findings of the survey conducted among 289 students across the country to assess the perception and use of video conferencing software platforms amid pandemic. Both online and offline questionnaires were distributed to find the targeted participants. The results reported that the majority of the participants (78.50%) could attend all the online classes through the conferencing platforms and the most used platforms were Google Meet (99%) and Zoom (98.60%). Participants were positively and negatively perceived the use of conferencing platforms for online learning and there existed gender differences in perceptions. Recorded lectures(66.8%), saving of time & effort (65.4%), and self-paced learning(56.7%) were the major benefits cited by the participants while lack of face to face interaction(72%), data scarcity(70.2%), poor audio(69.2%)&video(68.9%) quality and internet problems(66.8%) were the major hurdles in using the platforms. The participants expressed their desire for free internet data (95.80%) and user-friendly platforms (88.90%) for effective learning. Overall, a good number of participants (35.64%) were not satisfied with the use of video conferencing platforms for learning during the lockdown time. The results of this study would be helpful to revive the present online learning practices adopted in higher educational institutions to meet the needs of the students.

Keywords: - Online learning, Web learning, Distance learning, Videoconferencing, Video conferencing software, Education in India, COVID-19, Corona, Coronavirus.

I. INTRODUCTION

The outbreak of the deadly COVID-19 pandemic has devastated the entire educational system all over the globe (Anwar et al., 2020). As per UNICEF, more than 1 billion children were at risk of falling behind due to school closure (UNICEF, 2020). UNESCO reported that countries with nationwide closures have left 91.3% of their students out of learnings (Jogezai et al., 2021). Many institutions instructed the teachers to have online classes owing to the suspension of the physical classes to reduce the spread of the coronavirus (Moorhouse & Beaumont, 2020 & Rajhans et al., 2020). Many countries successfully adopted the synchronous mode of learning. While some other low-middle income countries largely regretted it due to the lack of infrastructure facilities and even due to religious beliefs in some communities (Jogezai et al., 2021). The adoption of web learning in pandemic hit countries showed promising results in terms of learning outcomes (Suprianto et al., 2020 & Gede et al., 2020). India, being a severely hit country also moved to the e-learning platforms for the continuity of the classes as the UGC insisted that “the educational institutes must strive to provide quality education, ensuring uniformity, equity, and universal accessibility to all the learners” (Rajhans et al., 2020). Before implementing and intensifying the distance mode of learning through web technologies, it is better to study how the students might have perceived and used the online conferencing software platforms for learning by assessing their current experiences. Previous studies were limited to some states or some communities and thus the present study was conducted covering the entire country irrespective of the division and domain of the pupils. The results of the current study would in fact help to modify the present distance learning technologies reeling in the country and also give hints for implementing the same productively after the post-pandemic period.

The entire study is driven by the following 3 prime questions,

- RQ:-1**What are the perceptions of Indian students in using the video conferencing software platforms for learning amid pandemic?
RQ:-2What are the major benefits and problems faced by the students in using the video conferencing software platforms for learning during pandemic times?
RQ:-3Are the students satisfied with the use of video conferencing platforms for learning? If 'No', what are their expectations to improve the learning through video conferencing software platforms?

II.PREVIOUS STUDIES

Literature detailing the perceptions of teachers and students regarding the implementation of online classes during the pandemic were reported from various countries (Chakraborty et al. (2021); Xie et al. (2020); Adnan & Anwar (2020) & Chen, Peng, et al. (2020)). This review of literature critically examines the positive and negative sides of online learning reported from different countries.

Suprianto et al. (2020) reported that learning outcomes after the online classes were increased when 39 students at the University of Borneo Tarakan, Indonesia were surveyed. 17.95% of the students agreed that their learning output was greatly improved due to the online classes. The improvement of learning outcomes by the online classes was reported by Gede et al. (2020) at STIKOM Yos Sudarso Purwokerto. In another similar kind of study, medical and dental students at the CMH medical college were reported to accommodate e-learning along with the current teaching practices as they found flexibility in the learning practices ($p=0.003$) and time savings ($p = 0.012$) (Anwar et al., 2020). Rajhans et al. (2020) discovered that 93.58% of the optometry educators in India had switched on to e-learning mode in a short time with good confidence. Anwar et al. (2020) reported that respondents encouraged the integration of e-learning into the current teaching practices. Respondents agreed that online study material provides flexibility in the learning process ($p= 0.003$) and save time ($p= 0.012$).

Ironically, Adnan & Anwar (2020) examined the attitude of Pakistani higher education students towards the compulsory digital and distance learning courses during the pandemic and found that online learning could not gain the desired results as the physical classes. The major hurdles faced by the students were internet problems and monetary issues. Bestiantono et al. (2020) from Indonesia presented the same findings that online learning could not bring the expected output among secondary students. Lack of face-to-face interaction between the students and the tutor was the major concern cited by the respondents. Students from New Zealand cited that online collaboration was not better compared to physical classes and so they could learn less in online learning (Yates et al., 2021). Krishnapatria (2020) after surveying students of International Business of Padjadjaran University reported that only 56% of the students were satisfied with e-learning. Pakaya et al. (2021) discovered that 30.4% of 214 students of Palako University disagreed that online lectures make it easier for them to interact to lecture. 43.7% of students experienced problems in communicating their learning problems with their lecture. Uma et al. (2020), Singh et al. (2020) and Ray et al. (2021) after surveying medical students in India reported the same findings that students were facing common problems like internet connectivity and lack of face to face interaction.

III.METHODS

3.1 Data collection and analysis

The study used a quantitative research design. An electronic questionnaire using Google Forms accessed at "https://docs.google.com/forms/d/1cF74kHw2OG_iVJqcrGZ8zfyW2KXdGFrsU8KF8NdOWXc/edit" was prepared to collect the data from the targeted participants. The questionnaire was prepared in English language and can be filled in within 2 to 3 minutes. The questionnaire consisted of 2 sections (*1st section -Demographic details and 2nd section -Regarding video conferencing platforms*) having 14 major questions to elicit the use (Q1), perception (Q8), benefits (Q9), hurdles (Q10), and challenges (Q11) of the participants in using the conferencing platforms for learning. A separate question was asked to assess the experiences (Q12) and expectations (Q13) of the participants for the effective use of platforms as well as their overall satisfaction (Q14). Along with the Google Forms questionnaire, the hardcopies of the questionnaire were also circulated. Thus, a total of 306 responses were received from 28th July 2021 to 30th August 2021 in which hardcopy consisted of 200 and the remaining was from Google Forms ie 106. Out of this, 289 participants were found using conferencing software platforms for learning amid the pandemic and the analysis was done on these samples set. The collected data from both hardcopies as well as electronic forms were merged and codified in a single Excel file for the subsequent analysis. The coded file was later uploaded to IBM-SPSS for analysis. Descriptive statistics including mean and SD was applied. To know the differences in the perceptions of video conferencing software platforms among male and female students, an independent sample t-test (Mann-Whitney U test) was applied.

3.2 Participants characteristics

The participants for this study were Indian students whose academic level ranged from high school to PhD/Postdoc. Out of the 289 participants, 181 (62.6%) were males and 108(37.4%) were females. The majority of the participants belonged to the age group of 21-25(43.9%) followed by 16-20(20.8%), 26-30(15.9%), 30+(14.5%), and also a few participants were between 11-15(4.8%). Concerning their level of study, the majority of them were with degree(35.6%) followed by postgraduation(31.1%), PhD/Postdoc(18.7%), high school(8.7%) and highersecondary/PUC(5.9%). With respect to the locality of the respondents, the majority of them were from a rural area (48.4%) followed by 118(40.8%) from urban and the remaining 31(10.7%) from semi-urban.

IV.RESULTS

Abbrev.Used:-VCSP=Video Conferencing Software Platforms

4.1 Use of video conferencing software platforms

Table 1 presents the results of the descriptive statistics of the use of video conferencing software platforms among the participants. As discussed in the methodology section, out of the 306 participants, 181(59.15%) male and 108(35.29%) female respondents reported using VCSP. Concerning the source of information of VCSP, the majority of the participants (74%) got to know about the platforms first from their teachers followed by internet sources(13.5%), friends(6.6%) and social media(4.2%). Concerning the devices that the participants used for accessing VCSP, the majority used their smartphone (84.8%) followed by laptop(31.5%),PC(11.8%) and tablet(11.1%).The majority of the respondents spent 5 to 6 hours using VCSP (39.1%).89(30.8%) of participants spent 3to 4 hours and only 9(.1%) spent more than 6 hours.

Table:-1 Use of video conferencing software platforms for learning

Response	Male	Female	Total
Use	181 (100%)	108 (100%)	289 (100%)
Source of information			
Friends	5 (2.8%)	14 (13%)	19 (6.6%)
Teachers	157 (86.7%)	57 (52.8%)	214 (74%)
Internet sources	14 (7.7%)	25 (23.1%)	39 (13.5%)
Social media	3 (1.7%)	9 (8.3%)	12 (4.2%)
Family/Relatives	0 (0%)	1 (.9%)	1 (.3%)
Other sources	2 (1.1%)	2 (1.9%)	4 (1.4%)
Device to access			
Smart phones	180 (99.4%)	65 (60.2%)	245 (84.8%)
Laptop	50 (27.6%)	41 (38%)	91 (31.5%)
PC	22 (12.2%)	12 (11.1%)	34 (11.8%)
Tablet	21 (11.6%)	11 (10.2%)	32 (11.1%)
Others	3 (1.7%)	3 (2.8%)	6 (2.1%)
Average time spending			
Below 1 hour	22 (12.2%)	6 (5.6%)	28 (9.7%)
1 to 2 hours	36 (19.9%)	14 (13%)	50 (17.3%)
3 to 4 hours	70	19	89

	(38.7%)	(17.6%)	(30.8%)
5 to 6 hours	53	60	113
	(29.3%)	(55.6%)	(39.1%)
Above 6 hours	0	9	9
	(0%)	(8.3%)	(3.1%)

4.2 Attendance of classes and Use of different video conferencing software platforms

Figure 1 shows the attendance of classes among the participants during the COVID-19 pandemic times through the VCSP.78.50% of the participants cited that they could attend all the classes followed by 10% posed they could attend some of the classes. Furthermore, 8.30% of the respondents could attend most of the classes but not all and 3.10% of them could attend class rarely. It was interesting to see that no participant could not attend the online classes during the pandemic. As per Figure 2, the most used VCSP among the participants were Google Meet and Zoom. The first one was used by 99% of the participants while the latter by 98.60% of the respondents. Other most-used platforms were WebEx (21.80%), YouTube Live(17.60%), Google Classroom(14.20%), Microsoft Teams (8.30%), Friends room(2.80%) and Microsoft 365(2.80%). The least used VCSP among the participants for the online classes were Learn Worlds and Educadium. Only 1% of the participants used these platforms.

[could attend all the classes, could attend most of the classes but not all, could attend some of the classes, could attend class rarely, could not attend the classes

Figure:-1 Attendance of classes

Figure:-2 Use of different VCSP among the participants

4.3 Perceptions regarding the use of video conferencing software platforms for learning

The data in Table 2 demonstrates the result of the descriptive statistics andMann-Whitney U test applied to assess the difference in the perceptions on the use of VCSP for learning among the male and female participants.

The highest mean response ie 4.04(SD=1.08) was observed for the last statement ie. “*Learning is the same in class and at home through the video conferencing software platforms*” and most of the participants disagreed with the statement. The least mean response showing the “agreement” observed for the statement “*I can complete the assignments and other works and can submit on time using video conferencing software platforms*” with Mean 1.75 (SD= .79). Five of the items had mean responses of 2.19(SD=.6), 2.06(SD=.63), 2.48(SD=.78), 2.78(SD=.89) and 2.96(SD=1.33) which were in the range of “2”, depicting the positive perception of VCSP for the learning. Similarly, five of the items had mean responses of 3.18(SD=1.13), 3.66(SD=1.31), 3.21(SD=1.03), 3.85(SD=1.34), 3.27(SD=1.33) and stood in the range of “3”, indicating that respondents perceptions were neutral to these statements. The result of the Mann-Whitney U test indicated that there existed a major difference between the genders regarding the perception of the use of VCSP for learning. Except for 3 statements (statement 3, 9 & 12), for all other statements, the p-value was less than the alpha value ($p < .005$).

Table:-2 Perceptions regarding the use of VCSP for learning

Response	Mean	SD	Z	P
I can easily access the video conferencing software platforms as needed for my studies	2.19	.96	-6.89	.000
I am comfortable communicating with my teachers and other classmates through video conferencing software platforms	3.18	1.13	-2.77	.005
I am willing to actively communicate with my teachers and other classmates through video conferencing software platforms	3.66	1.31	-.694	.488
I feel that my learning experiences will be beneficial to my studies using video conferencing software platforms	2.06	.63	-6.83	.000
I am comfortable with written communication (for example via the chat box in a video conferencing software platform)	2.48	.78	-5.54	.000
I believe looking back on what I have learned in a course through video conferencing software platforms will help me to remember it better	3.21	1.03	-3.96	.000
I can manage my study time effectively and easily by using video conferencing software platforms	2.78	.89	-4.42	.000
I can complete the assignments and other works and can submit on time using video conferencing software platforms	1.75	.79	-9.72	.000
I feel comfortable communicating online in English through video conferencing software platforms	3.85	1.34	-.980	.327
I feel that face-to-face contact with my tutor/teacher is necessary to learn.	3.27	1.33	-2.99	.003
I am motivated by the material in an online activity outside of class through video conferencing software platforms	2.96	1.33	-7.57	.000
Learning is the same in class and at home through the video conferencing software platforms	4.04	1.08	-1.45	.146

4.4 Benefits of using video conferencing software platforms for learning

Table 3 discusses the major benefits of using VCSP for learning. According to the table, 56.7% of the participants agreed that the use of VCSP helped them for self-paced learning with a mean response of 2.50(SD=.63). More than half of the respondents (52.6%) were neutral to the statement of VCSP helped them to improve their communication. Similarly, more than half of them (50.2%) cited the benefits of multimedia learning with a mean response of 2.68(SD=.76). The majority of the participants (66.8%) agreed that recorded lectures were beneficial to them followed by it could save time and effort with a mean response of 2.45(SD=.68). However, most of the participants (62.3%) not agreed that VCSP could increase the overall efficiency. In total, out of 6 items, participants were positively reacted to 4 statements regarding the benefits of VCSP for learning and the rest of the two statements were of the neutral status.

Table:-3 Benefits of using video conferencing software platforms for learning

Response	Agree (2)	Neutral (3)	Disagree (4)	Mean	SD
Self-paced learning	164 (56.7%)	103 (35.6%)	22 (7.6%)	2.50	.63

Improved communication	54 (18.7%)	152 (52.6%)	83 (28.7%)	3.1	.68
Multimedia learning	145 (50.2%)	90 (31.1%)	54 (18.7%)	2.68	.76
Recorded lectures	193 (66.8%)	65 (22.5%)	31 (10.7%)	2.43	.68
Save time and efforts	189 (65.4%)	69 (23.9%)	31 (10.7%)	2.45	.68
Overall increased efficiency	53 (18.3%)	180 (62.3%)	56 (19.4%)	3.01	.61

4.5 Problems faced in using video conferencing software platforms for learning

Table 4 demonstrates the major problems faced by the participants in using VCSP for learning measured on a 5 point Likert scale from 'Always to Never' and analyzed by descriptive statistics. Out of the 10 items, 2 items i.e. items no 8&9 received a mean response of 2.27(SD=.91) and 2.07(SD=.74) which were in the range of 2 and treated as problems that the participants encountered often. The rest of the items received a mean response in the range '1' and were considered as the hurdles that they faced always while hooked on VCSP for learning. The most severe problem as cited by the participants was data scarcity (Mean=1.2, SD=.92) and lack of face to face interaction (Mean=1.42, SD=.79). The other severe problems were internet problems (Mean=1.52, SD=.82), poor audio (Mean=1.56, SD=.94) and video quality (Mean=1.57, SD=.96), health issues (Mean=1.68, SD=.90), technical and network issues (Mean=1.70, SD=.82).

Table:-4 Problems faced in using video conferencing software platforms for learning

Response	Always (1)	Often (2)	Sometimes (3)	Ever (4)	Never (5)	Mean	SD
Technical issues and Network issues	147 (50.9%)	85 (29.4%)	55 (19%)	0 (0%)	2 (.7%)	1.70	.82
Internet problems	193 (66.8%)	47 (16.3%)	45 (15.6%)	2 (.7%)	2 (.7%)	1.52	.82
Health issues	153 (52.9%)	92 (31.8%)	35 (12.1%)	1 (.3%)	8 (2.8%)	1.68	.90
No face to face interaction	208 (72%)	47 (16.3%)	29 (10%)	1 (.3%)	4 (1.4%)	1.42	.79
Difficult to use	159 (55%)	57 (19.7%)	50 (17.3%)	3 (1%)	20 (6.9%)	1.85	1.17
Poor video quality	199 (68.9%)	30 (10.4%)	51 (17.6%)	2 (.7%)	7 (2.4%)	1.57	.96
Poor audio quality	200 (69.2%)	28 (9.7%)	52 (18%)	4 (1.4%)	5 (1.7%)	1.56	.94
Monotonous	70 (24.2%)	87 (30.1%)	121 (41.9%)	6 (2.1%)	5 (1.7%)	2.27	.91
Increased fatigue	48 (16.6%)	187 (64.7%)	44 (15.2%)	4 (1.4%)	6 (2.1%)	2.07	.74

Data scarcity	203	42	34	2	8	1.2	.92
	(70.2%)	(14.5%)	(11.8%)	(.7%)	(2.8%)		

4.6 Experiences in using video conferencing software platforms

Experiences of the participants in using VCSP amid the pandemic was measured by using a 5 point Likert scale with 1 strongly agreeing to 5 strongly disagreeing. The result of the descriptive statistics showed that only for 1 item, the participants disagreed i.e. ‘Instant reply to students questions’ with a mean response of 3.79(SD=1.37). The majority of the participants (79.9%) strongly agreed that there was a clear difference between the online and offline classes (Mean=1.28, SD=.63) and 77.2% of the respondents opined that the effectiveness of a teacher's class was not the same between offline and online mode (Mean=1.32, SD=.66). However, more than half of the participants agreed that the lecturer/ instructor used the relevant instructional medium (Mean=1.93, SD=.66) and the content of the sessions met their expectations (Mean=2.08, SD=1.05). 73.35% of the participants agreed that the workload through the online classes was high with a mean response of 1.82(SD=.92).

Table:-5 Experiences in using video conferencing software platforms for learning

Response	Strongly Agree(1)	Agree (2)	Neutral (3)	Disagree (4)	Strongly Disagree(5)	Mean	SD
Lecturer/ Instructor used the relevant instructional medium	72 (24.9%)	167 (57.8%)	49 (17%)	0 (0%)	1 (.3%)	1.93	.66
The content of the sessions met my expectations	110 (38.1%)	87 (30.1%)	51 (17.6%)	41 (14.2%)	0 (0%)	2.08	1.05
Group discussions were found useful	23 (8.0%)	90 (31.1%)	158 (54.7%)	17 (5.9%)	1 (.3%)	2.59	.73
Workload was high	140 (48.4%)	72 (24.9%)	70 (24.2%)	3 (1.0%)	4 (1.4%)	1.82	.92
Instant reply to students' questions	25 (8.7%)	40 (13.8%)	39 (13.5%)	50 (17.3%)	135 (46.7%)	3.79	1.37
Easy Information/ Materials access from online tools	27 (9.3%)	76 (26.3%)	173 (59.9%)	13 (4.5%)	0 (0%)	2.59	.72
There is a clear difference between offline and online classes	231 (79.9%)	38 (13.1%)	17 (5.9%)	2 (.7%)	1 (.3%)	1.28	.63
The effectiveness of a teacher's class is not the same between offline and online mode	223 (77.2%)	42 (14.5%)	20 (6.9%)	4(1.4%)	0 (0%)	1.32	.66

4.7 Requirements/desires for effective use and Overall satisfaction

Figure 3 depicts the results of the participants' desire for improving the effective use of the VCSP for learning. Most of the participants (95.80%) expressed their desire for free internet data for the continuation of learning

amid the pandemic. 88.90% of the respondents communicated the preference for VCSP that were easy to access followed by 85.50 % who indicated their desire towards a free device for use. A good number of participants also exhibited their requirement towards the training for the use (80.60%). The need for increased internet speed at home was expressed by 31.50% of the total participants. As per Figure 4, the majority of the participants showed a positive fulfilment (7.30%= highly satisfied & 33.20%= satisfied) towards the use of VCSP for learning purposes. However, there were 32.90% of dissatisfied participants and 2.80% of participants were highly dissatisfied. The number of participants who expressed neutral was 23.90%.

Figure:-3 Requirements for effective use of VCSP for learning

Figure:-4 Overall satisfaction

V.FINDINGS, DISCUSSIONS & CONCLUSION

The present study was carried out to assess the perception of the Indian students on the use of video conferencing software platforms for learning amid pandemic times. The survey results reported interesting findings. As per our findings, no student missed the classes during pandemic times and the majority could participate in all the online classes through the VCSP. The daily average spending time on these platforms also confirms the same. Similar to previous studies (Kumar et al., 2020 & Adhikari et al., 2020), our study also discovered that Google Meet and Zoom were the most used platforms among Indian students. When the perception regarding the use of VCSP was assessed, the study reported that students perceived both positively and negatively and existed a major difference between the genders regarding the perception of the use of VCSP for learning. Concerning the benefits of the VCSP, participants expressed that it could enhance the self-paced learning of them and recorded lectures helped them to save time and efforts. However, when asked regarding the improvement of communication through VCSP, majority of them were neutral which might be because of the monotonous nature of the classes which was evident from Table 4. Similar to many previous studies (Adhikari et al., 2020; Siddiqui et al., 2021 & Kaur & Sharma, 2020), our findings were also parallel as far as the major hurdles faced by the participants. Lack of face to face

interaction, technical issues and network issues, internet connectivity problems and data scarcity were the major problems faced by the students. Apart from these issues, health issues were also reported which might be due to the excess workload as indicated by the participants. This does not seem like an odd event and Adhikari et al. (2020) reported from Nepal that more than half of the students faced some sort of visual problems due to online classes. Siddiqui et al. (2021) reported that the majority of the students of Liaquat University of Medical and Health Sciences, Jamshorofelt stress on submitting assignments and appearing on the online test. Participants also raised concern that faculties failed to respond lively to the student's questions. When the desires of the participants were sought, the majority demanded the need for free internet data, free devices and training on use. Overall, our study found that most of the participants were not satisfied in online classes through the VCSP. A similar kind of study conducted by Kaur & Sharma (2020) among nursing students in Himachal Pradesh also reported that students were only partially satisfied and expressed that they did not prefer online classes after the pandemic (Adhikari et al., 2020).

The COVID-19 pandemic is a disruptor to the present educational system which offered an opportunity to revive the traditional classroom-based educational system. The transition to technology-based learning has helped the stakeholders to keep the continuity of the classes while keeping the students and faculties stay out of trouble. Even though our study reported that the online classes' through VCSP was not up to the mark, similar kind of studies from other countries reported the positive side of the VCSP - based learning. So, it is high time to modify the present online education strategies for meeting the needs of the students in the country. Furthermore, as the perception of students on the use of VCSP for learning found positive, it can be suggested that technology-based distance learning through video conferencing platforms can be considered for the post-COVID period as an effective way of taking classes after finding the solution to the problems faced by the students reported in the current study.

REFERENCES

- [1] Anwar, A.; Mansoor, H.; Faisal, D.; & Khan, H. S. E-Learning amid the COVID-19 Lockdown: Standpoint of Medical and Dental Undergraduates. *Pakistan J. Med. Sci.*, 2020, **37** (1), 1–6. <https://doi.org/10.12669/pjms.37.1.3124> (Accessed on 29 August 2021).
- [2] UNICEF. Education and COVID-19 <https://data.unicef.org/topic/education/covid-19/> (accessed Aug 30, 2021).
- [3] Jomezai, N. A.; Baloch, F. A.; Jaffar, M.; Shah, T.; Khilji, G. K.; & Bashir, S. Teachers' Attitudes towards Social Media (SM) Use in Online Learning amid the COVID-19 Pandemic: The Effects of SM Use by Teachers and Religious Scholars during Physical Distancing. *Heliyon*, 2021, **7** (4), e06781. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2021.e06781> (Accessed on 29 August 2021).
- [4] Moorhouse, B. L.; & Beaumont, A. M. Utilizing Video Conferencing Software to Teach Young Language Learners in Hong Kong during the COVID-19 Class Suspensions. *TESOL J.*, 2020, **11** (3). <https://doi.org/10.1002/tesj.545> (Accessed on 29 August 2021).
- [5] Rajhans, V.; Memon, U.; Patil, V.; & Goyal, A. Impact of COVID-19 on Academic Activities and Way Forward in Indian Optometry. *J. Optom.*, 2020, **13** (4), 216–226. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.optom.2020.06.002> (Accessed on 29 August 2021).
- [6] Suprianto, S.; Arhas, S. H.; & Mahmuddin, M. The Effectiveness of Online Learning Amid the COVID-19 Pandemic. *J. Ad'ministrare*, 2020, **7** (2), 321–330. <https://doi.org/10.26858/ja.v7i2.16441> (Accessed on 29 August 2021).
- [7] Gede, I.; Suci, S.; Suyanta, W.; Darna, W.; Wijoyo, H.; & Setyawati, E. *A Measure of Effectiveness Level of Online Learning Amid COVID-19 Pandemic in the Course of the Project Management Information Systems (Case Study in Stikom Yos Sudarso Purwokerto)*; 2020. <https://doi.org/10.31838/jcr.07.12.586> (Accessed on 29 August 2021).
- [8] Chakraborty, P.; Mittal, P.; Gupta, M. S.; Yadav, S.; & Arora, A. Opinion of Students on Online Education during the COVID-19 Pandemic. *Hum. Behav. Emerg. Technol.*, 2021, **3** (3), 357–365. <https://doi.org/10.1002/hbe2.240> (Accessed on 29 August 2021).
- [9] Xie, X.; Siau, K.; & Nah, F. F.-H. COVID-19 Pandemic – Online Education in the New Normal and the next Normal. *J. Inf. Technol. Case Appl. Res.*, 2020, **22** (3), 175–187. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15228053.2020.1824884> (Accessed on 29 August 2021).
- [10] Adnan, M.; & Anwar, K. Online Learning amid the COVID-19 Pandemic: Students Perspectives. *J. Pedagog. Social. Psychol.*, 2020, **1** (2), 45–51. <https://doi.org/10.33902/JPSP.2020261309> (Accessed on 29 August 2021).
- [11] Chen, T.; Peng, L.; Jing, B.; Wu, C.; Yang, J.; & Cong, G. The Impact of the COVID-19 Pandemic on User Experience with Online Education Platforms in China. *Sustainability*, 2020, **12** (18), 7329. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su12187329> (Accessed on 30 August 2021).
- [12] Bestiantono, D. S.; Agustina, P. Z. R.; & Cheng, T.-H. How Students' Perspectives about Online Learning Amid the COVID-19 Pandemic? *Stud. Learn. Teach.*, 2020, **7** (2), 321–330. <https://doi.org/10.46627/silet.v1i3.46> (Accessed on 25 August 2021).

- [13] Yates, A.; Starkey, L.; Egerton, B.; & Flueggen, F. High School Students' Experience of Online Learning during Covid-19: The Influence of Technology and Pedagogy. *Technol. Pedagog. Educ.*, 2021. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1475939X.2020.1854337>(Accessed on 20August 2021).
- [14] Krishnapatria, K. From 'Lockdown' to Letdown: Students' Perception of E-Learning amid the COVID-19 Outbreak. *ELT Focus*, 2020. <https://doi.org/10.35706/eltinf.v3i1.3694>(Accessed on 27August 2021).
- [15] Pakaya, D.; Towidjojo, V. D.; & Demak, I. P. K. Medical Student's Perception of Online Learning in Tadulako University During COVID-19 Pandemic. In *Proceedings of the 3rd International Conference on Educational Development and Quality Assurance (ICED-QA 2020)*; 2021. <https://doi.org/10.2991/assehr.k.210202.031>(Accessed on 29August 2021).
- [16] Uma, G.; Vartika, T.; & Kumar, G. N. Perception about Online Learning among Medical Students in Northern India during Lockdown Period of Covid - 19: A Cross-Sectional Study. *Int. J. Contemp. Med. Res.*, 2020, **7** (12).
- [17] Singh, K. V.; Aqeel, K. I.; & Misra, S. K. A Cross-Sectional Study of Perception among Medical Students on Online Learning amid COVID-19 Pandemic, at Government Medical College, Agra, India. *Int. J. Community Med. Public Heal.*, 2020. <https://doi.org/10.18203/2394-6040.ijcmph20205702>(Accessed on 29 August 2021).
- [18] Ray, I.; Agarwal, V.; Agarwal, T.; & Pande, A. Medical Student's Perspective Regarding Undergraduate Surgical Education with Special Reference to Pandemic. *Indian J. Surg.*, 2021. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12262-021-02904-0>(Accessed on 29August 2021).
- [19] Kumar, G.; Singh, G.; Bhatnagar, V.; Gupta, R.; & Upadhyay, S. K. Outcome of Online Teaching-Learning over Traditional Education during Covid-19 Pandemic. *Int. J. Adv. Trends Comput. Sci. Eng.*, 2020. <https://doi.org/10.30534/ijatcse/2020/113952020>(Accessed on 30August 2021).
- [20] Adhikari, P.; Paudel, S.; Pandey, R. R.; Parajuli, A.; & Pyakuryal, A. Effectiveness of E-Learning during the COVID-19 Pandemic among the Undergraduate Medical Students in Nepal: An Online Survey. *J. Pharm. Pract. Community Med.*, 2020. <https://doi.org/10.5530/jppcm.2020.3.13>(Accessed on 29August 2021).
- [21] Siddiqui, M. I.; Shah, R.; & Ariser, K. N. Challenges of Online Learning and Attitude of Medical Student at LUMHS: Comparative Study among Rural and Urban Students during Covid -19 Pandemic. *Med. Forum*, 2021, **32** (5), 82–86.
- [22] Kaur, S.; & Sharma, A. Online Classes of Nursing Students during Lockdown (Covid Pandemic): Perception and Issues. *Int. J. Adv. Res.*, 2020, **8** (8), 494–500. <https://doi.org/10.21474/IJAR01/11518>(Accessed on 29 August 2021).